

Organic Pesticides. Part XI. Synthesis of 2-Arylamino-4-substituted Phenyl- and 2-Arylamino-4-substituted Phenyl-5-methyl-thiazoles

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Seven 2-arylamino-4-(2'-hydroxy-5'-fluoro)phenyl-, and six 2-arylamino-4-(2'-hydroxy-5'-fluoro)-phenyl-5-methyl-thiazoles have been synthesised with a view to studying their pesticidal properties.

In view of the thiazole derivatives exhibiting wide range of different biological activities, the authors considered it worthwhile to synthesise the title compounds for screening their pesticidal properties. Since an unsubstituted heterocycle is seldom toxic and that the addition of a lipophilic substituent, either aryl or alkyl, often induces toxicity¹, we have consequently attempted to introduce the said substituents in thiazole nucleus to obtain compounds of potential toxicity. In this investigation, we were further prompted by certain observations like, 4-methyl- or phenyl-substituted 2-hydroxythiazole being insecticidal², 2-arylamino-4,5 dimethylthiazole being fungitoxic³, and the fact that no study on such fluoro-substitutions in thiazole nucleus has apparently been undertaken so far.

The 2-arylamino-4-(2'-hydroxy-5'-fluoro)phenylthiazoles were obtained by treating arylthioureas with 2-hydroxy-5-fluoro-acetophenone in presence of iodine following the method of King and Hlavacek⁴. The 2-arylamino-4-(2'-hydroxy-5'-fluoro)phenyl-5-methylthiazoles were similarly prepared from arylthioureas and 2-hydroxy-5-fluoro-propionophenone. The arylthioureas were prepared from appropriate amines following the method of Douglass and Dains⁵.

The required hydroxyketones were obtained by the Fries migration of acetate and propionate of *p*-fluorophenol in the usual way. The acetates and propionates were prepared by interaction of the corresponding acid chloride and *p*-fluorophenol, following the method of Spasov.⁶

EXPERIMENTAL

m-Fluoronitrobenzene was prepared by the Balz-Schiemann reaction⁷ from *m*-nitroaniline (25 g.); yield 15 g. (58.8%), b.p. 71-72°/12-15 mm. Ingold and Vass⁸ record b.p. 199-200°.

1. Horsfall and Rich, "Contributions From Boyce Thompson Institute", 1951, 16, 346.
2. Grove *et al.*, *Ann. Appl. Biol.*, 1947, 34, 113.
3. Das *et al.*, *this Journal*, 1955, 32, 55.
4. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 3722.
5. *Ibid.*, 1934, 56, 1408.
6. *Chem. Abst.*, 1940, 34, 2342.
7. Adams, "Organic Reactions", Vol. V, p. 203.
8. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 421.

m-Fluoroaniline was obtained by reducing *m*-fluoronitrobenzene (15 g.) in the usual way with a mixture of iron dust (18.8 g.), HCl (conc., 6.5 ml) and water (12.5 ml); yield 6.5 g. (55%), b.p. 102-103°/30 mm. Ingold and Vass⁸ record b.p. 187-89°.

Arylthioureas were prepared according to the method of Douglass and Dains⁵ by the interaction of a mixture of benzoyl chloride (0.1 *M*) and ammonium thiocyanate (0.1 *M*) in dry acetone (25 ml) and a solution of appropriate amine (0.1 *M*) in acetone (25 ml) and isolating the products in the usual way. The arylthioureas thus obtained were: phenyl, *m*-chlorophenyl, *p*-tolyl, *p*-anisyl, *m*-fluorophenyl, 2,4,6-tribromophenyl, 2,5-dichlorophenyl, and 2-pyridyl, the melting points of which were in good agreement with those previously recorded.

TABLE I

2-Arylamino-substituted thiazoles.

No. Aryl.	M.P.	% Yield.	Formula.	% Sulphur.	
				Found.	Reqd.
R=H.					
1. Phenyl	125-26°	56.0	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ ON ₂ FS	10.53	11.18
2. <i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	99-100°	60.5	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ ON ₂ ClFS	9.20	9.98
3. 2,5-Dichlorophenyl	160°	63.2	C ₁₃ H ₉ ON ₂ Cl ₂ FS	10.20	9.01
4. <i>p</i> -Anisyl	195°	45.0	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ FS	9.74	10.12
5. 2,4,6-Tribromophenyl	210°	48.0	C ₁₃ H ₆ ON ₂ Br ₃ FS	5.14	6.11
6. <i>m</i> -Fluorophenyl	214-15°	52.3	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ ON ₂ F ₂ S	10.00	10.52
7. 2-Pyridyl	164-65°	49.0	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ ON ₂ FS	10.62	11.15
R=Me.					
8. Phenyl	134-35°	70.5	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ ON ₂ FS	10.02	10.66
9. <i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	90-91°	55.4	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ ON ₂ ClFS	10.04	9.56
10. 2,5-Dichlorophenyl	172-73°	50.2	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ ON ₂ Cl ₂ FS	8.51	8.67
11. <i>m</i> -Fluorophenyl	113-14°	48.8	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ ON ₂ F ₂ S	10.51	10.06
12. <i>p</i> -Tolyl	167-68°	41.4	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ ON ₂ FS	9.93	10.10
13. 2-Pyridyl	85-86°	50.6	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ ON ₂ FS	10.84	10.63

p-Fluorophenyl acetate was prepared by the method of Spasov⁶ by refluxing a mixture of *p*-fluorophenol (22.4 g.), acetyl chloride (15.7 g.), and magnesium ribbon (2.4 g.) in anhydrous benzene (50 ml) for 2 hours and isolating the product in the usual way; yield 24 g. (77.8%), b.p. 54-55°/4-5 mm. Heilbron and Bunbury⁹ report b.p. 85-87°/16 mm.

p-Fluorophenyl propionate was prepared by the above method from *p*-fluorophenol (22.4 g.) and propionyl chloride (18.5 g.) in 28 g. yield (83.3%); b.p. 118-20°/18-20 mm. Literature¹⁰ records b.p. 95-96°/15 mm.

9. "Dictionary of Organic Compounds".

10. *Chem. Abst.*, 1955, 49, 13923.

2-Hydroxy-5-fluoroacetophenone was prepared by refluxing a mixture of *p*-fluorophenyl acetate (24 g.) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (32 g.) for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour and isolating the product in the customary way; yield 15 g. (62.5%), b.p. 65-66°/8 mm. Buu. Hoi *et al.*¹¹ record b.p. 103-104°/13 mm.

2-Hydroxy-5-fluoropropiophenone was obtained by above method from *p*-fluorophenyl propionate (28 g.); yield 16 g. (57%), b.p. 97-99°/6-7 mm. Buu. Hoi *et al.*¹¹ record b.p. 111-12°/13 mm.

2-Arylamino-substituted Thiazoles.—A mixture of arylthiourea (2*M*), 2-hydroxy-5-fluoroketone (1*M*), and iodine (1*M*) was refluxed for 20 to 24 hours. The crude product was kept in contact with ether for 16 to 20 hours to remove the unchanged ketone. The residue was shaken with sodium thiosulphate solution to remove the last traces of iodine, boiled with water, and filtered hot. The solid cake left behind was treated with NH₄OH (conc., in some cases refluxed with NH₄OH) and the precipitated thiazole was crystallised from aqueous ethanol except in two cases where the crystalline products were isolated only after keeping their solution in toluene in cold for several days. The thiazoles, thus prepared, are recorded in Table I.

The evaluation of the pesticidal activity of these compounds is under investigation and will be communicated in due course.

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11. *J. Org. Chem.*, 1954, 19, 1617.